

The Function of *Wayyiqtol* in Biblical Hebrew:

A Discourse-Oriented Reassessment of the *Waw-Consecutive* Construction

Željko Stanojević

Institute for Hebrew Language and Literature, Belgrade

ORCID: 0009-0009-0717-6184

Abstract

The *wayyiqtol* construction represents one of the most distinctive and widely debated features of the verbal system of Biblical Hebrew. Traditionally interpreted within the framework of the so-called *waw conversive*, this construction has long been understood as a combination of the conjunction *waw* and an imperfect verbal form whose temporal value is “reversed” to express past action. This interpretation has significantly influenced both grammatical descriptions and the translation of biblical texts into numerous languages.

The present study offers a comprehensive reassessment of the *wayyiqtol* construction by integrating grammatical, discourse-linguistic, and translational perspectives. Through a detailed analysis of narrative texts from the Hebrew Bible, it is demonstrated that *wayyiqtol* functions primarily as a marker of sequential progression within the narrative structure, rather than as a simple expression of tense conversion. Particular attention is devoted to the distinction between foreground and background information, where *wayyiqtol* consistently marks the main line of events, while other verbal forms are used for descriptive or contextual purposes.

In addition, the study examines the historical development of the translational tradition, beginning with the Septuagint and the Latin Vulgate and extending to modern European translations. It is shown that the widespread rendering of *wayyiqtol* as “and + verb” reflects the influence of these traditions and contributes to the perception of *waw* as a coordinating conjunction. However, this interpretation does not fully correspond to the discourse function of the construction in the Hebrew text.

Building on contemporary linguistic approaches, including theories of grammaticalization and discourse analysis, the study proposes that *wayyiqtol* should be understood as a unified grammatical form whose primary function is to structure narrative progression. Within this framework, the prefix *waw* is not treated as an independent conjunction but as an integral component of a grammaticalized construction.

The results of this study have important implications for both the interpretation and translation of biblical texts. By emphasizing the discourse function of *wayyiqtol*, the study provides a more

coherent account of the Hebrew verbal system and offers a foundation for more precise and context-sensitive translation strategies.

Keywords

Biblical Hebrew; *wayyiqtol*; *waw consecutive*; *waw conversive*; Hebrew verbal system; discourse analysis; narrative structure; grammaticalization; Septuagint; Vulgate; Bible translation; Hebrew linguistics

1. Introduction

One of the most characteristic and most frequently discussed grammatical phenomena in Biblical Hebrew is the so-called *wayyiqtol* construction, traditionally known as *waw consecutive* or earlier *waw conversive*. This construction plays a central role in the narrative texts of the Hebrew Bible, particularly in historical and narrative sections such as the books of Genesis, Exodus, Judges, and Samuel. It is precisely through this form that the biblical text achieves a continuous flow of narration, linking individual actions into a sequence of events that constitutes the backbone of narrative structure.

Morphologically, *wayyiqtol* consists of the prefix ו (waw) attached to a verbal form traditionally identified as the imperfect. Typical examples include forms such as *wayyō'mer* ("he said"), *wayyar* ("he saw"), *wayya'as* ("he did"), and *wayyiqra* ("he called"). These forms dominate narrative passages and frequently appear in extended sequences, creating a structure in which actions follow one another consecutively.

In classical grammatical descriptions of Biblical Hebrew, this construction has been interpreted as the result of a specific function of the prefix waw, which allegedly "reverses" or "converts" the temporal value of the verb.¹ Based on such an interpretation, the term *waw conversive* was developed, referring to the idea that waw alters verbal tense, transforming the imperfect into a past tense or, in other contexts, the perfect into a future tense.²

This explanation dominated classical Hebraic scholarship, particularly in grammatical works of the nineteenth and early twentieth centuries. According to this approach, waw was primarily understood as a coordinating conjunction which, in combination with certain verbal forms, produces a specific temporal effect.³ In translations of the biblical text, this interpretation was most often reflected in the literal rendering of the structure "and + verb," which became a nearly standard feature of biblical style in many European languages.⁴

However, modern linguistic research increasingly questions the adequacy of the traditional *waw conversive* explanation. In recent grammatical and discourse-based analyses of Biblical Hebrew, *wayyiqtol* is no longer viewed as the result of a “conversion” of verbal tense but rather as a specific narrative form with a primarily discourse function.⁵ According to this approach, *wayyiqtol* serves above all as a marker of sequentiality, that is, as a device signaling the main line of narrative progression.⁶

Footnotes (sample)

1. Wilhelm Gesenius, *Gesenius' Hebrew Grammar*, ed. E. Kautzsch, rev. A. E. Cowley (Oxford: Clarendon Press, 1910), §§111–112.
2. *Ibid.*
3. Paul Joüon and Takamitsu Muraoka, *A Grammar of Biblical Hebrew* (Rome: Pontifical Biblical Institute, 2006), §118.
4. Bruce K. Waltke and Michael O'Connor, *An Introduction to Biblical Hebrew Syntax* (Winona Lake: Eisenbrauns, 1990).
5. John A. Cook, “The Hebrew Verb: A Grammaticalization Approach,” *Journal of Semitic Studies* 52 (2007): 239–280.
6. Alviero Niccacci, *Syntax of the Verb in Classical Hebrew Prose* (Sheffield: JSOT Press, 1990).

2. Survey of Previous Scholarship

The question of the function of the *wayyiqtol* construction in Biblical Hebrew has long occupied a central place in grammatical and linguistic studies devoted to the Old Testament. Over the past two centuries, a wide range of interpretations has been developed in an attempt to explain the relationship between the prefix *waw* and the verbal form that follows it. These interpretations may broadly be divided into three major groups: the traditional theory of *waw conversive*, modern grammatical analyses that interpret *wayyiqtol* as a specific narrative preterite, and discourse-oriented approaches that analyze this construction within the structure of narrative text.¹

One of the most influential traditional explanations originates in nineteenth-century grammatical scholarship, particularly in the grammar developed by Wilhelm Gesenius.² In this approach, the theory known as *waw conversive* or *waw consecutive* was formulated. According to this model, the prefix *waw* functions as an element that changes or “reverses” the temporal value of the verb with which it occurs. In the case of the imperfect, the addition of *waw* is said to transform the verb into a form expressing past action, while in other contexts it may have the opposite effect.³ Thus, a construction such as *wayyō' mer* is interpreted as a combination of the conjunction “and” with an imperfect verb whose temporal value has been altered by the presence of the prefix *waw*.

This theory dominated the study of Biblical Hebrew for a long time and had a significant influence on how grammarians and translators understood the structure of narrative texts. Within

this framework, the prefix *waw* was primarily viewed as a coordinating conjunction, while its effect on verbal tense was explained as a special syntactic-morphological phenomenon characteristic of Hebrew. Although the term *waw conversive* was later often replaced by the more neutral expression *waw consecutive*, the basic idea of “tense reversal” remained present in a large number of grammatical descriptions.⁴

During the second half of the twentieth century, however, an increasing number of linguists began to question the adequacy of this explanation. Modern grammars of Biblical Hebrew increasingly abandon the notion of mechanical “tense reversal” and instead attempt to explain *wayyiqtol* within the broader system of verbal forms. Particularly significant in this regard are the works of Bruce Waltke and Michael O’Connor, whose grammar of Biblical Hebrew represents one of the most influential modern references in the field.⁵ In their approach, *wayyiqtol* is viewed as the primary narrative form that advances the action within a story. Rather than focusing on tense transformation, these authors emphasize the function of sequentiality and highlight the crucial role of *wayyiqtol* in organizing the narrative flow.

A similar approach can be found in the grammar developed by Paul Joüon and Takamitsu Muraoka.⁶ In their description of Biblical Hebrew, *wayyiqtol* is interpreted as a special form characteristic of narrative texts, serving to mark the sequence of events in the past. Although their analysis still acknowledges the historical connection of this construction with the prefix *waw*, the emphasis shifts from the idea of temporal transformation toward an understanding of its narrative function.

In more recent linguistic studies, this tendency becomes even more pronounced. John Cook, for example, in his work on the verbal system of Biblical Hebrew, proposes that *wayyiqtol* represents a narrative preterite, that is, a form functioning as the primary means of expressing sequential past events.⁷ Within this model, the construction is not viewed as a combination of conjunction and verb, but as part of a broader system of verbal forms with specific discourse functions.

A similar position is advocated by Robert Holmstedt, who emphasizes in his linguistic analyses that the prefix *waw* in these constructions does not necessarily function as a coordinating conjunction.⁸ Instead, it may be understood as an element that, through historical linguistic development, became integrated into a specialized narrative form. Holmstedt’s analysis particularly highlights the importance of syntactic and discourse context in interpreting this construction, arguing that its function cannot be adequately explained solely in terms of traditional tense categories.

In addition to these grammatical approaches, significant contributions to the study of *wayyiqtol* have also been made by scholars applying discourse analysis. In the works of Alviero Niccacci, a theory has been developed according to which Biblical Hebrew narrative exhibits a clearly structured hierarchy of verbal forms.⁹ Within this framework, *wayyiqtol* marks the main line of narration—that is, the sequence of events that propel the action forward—while other verbal forms are used to describe background, circumstances, or states. This analysis demonstrates that the function of *wayyiqtol* is not merely grammatical but also discourse-related, as it plays a central role in structuring the text.

A similar approach can be found in the work of Robert Longacre, who applied text-linguistic methods to the study of biblical narratives.¹⁰ Longacre demonstrated that in many narrative texts, a clear distinction can be identified between verbs that carry the main action and those that serve as background elements. Within this framework, *wayyiqtol* appears as the dominant form signaling the continuation of the narrative sequence, thereby confirming its central role in narrative structure.

The review of this scholarship shows that there is a broad consensus among contemporary researchers regarding the central function of *wayyiqtol* in the narrative discourse of Biblical Hebrew. However, despite this consensus, the question remains open as to how this function should be interpreted in relation to the prefix *waw* and its traditional identification as a coordinating conjunction.

It is precisely at this point that space emerges for further analysis. The interpretation presented in this study aligns with contemporary linguistic approaches in emphasizing the narrative function of the *wayyiqtol* construction and its role in marking the sequential progression of events. However, it diverges from certain existing models in its understanding of the relationship between the prefix *waw* and the perception of this construction within the translational tradition. While most grammatical studies focus on the internal structure of Hebrew, the present study pays particular attention to how historical translations have contributed to the interpretation of *waw* as primarily a coordinating conjunction.

In this way, the study seeks to connect the grammatical analysis of Biblical Hebrew with the history of its translation and reception in different linguistic traditions. Such an approach allows the problem of the *wayyiqtol* construction to be viewed not only as a matter of linguistic structure but also as a matter of interpretation shaped over centuries through the processes of translation and reading of the biblical text.

Footnotes

1. For an overview of theories on *waw consecutive*, see Bruce K. Waltke and Michael O'Connor, *An Introduction to Biblical Hebrew Syntax* (Winona Lake: Eisenbrauns, 1990).
2. Wilhelm Gesenius, *Gesenius' Hebrew Grammar*, ed. E. Kautzsch, rev. A. E. Cowley (Oxford: Clarendon Press, 1910).
3. Gesenius, *Hebrew Grammar*, §§111–112.
4. Paul Joüon and Takamitsu Muraoka, *A Grammar of Biblical Hebrew* (Rome: Pontifical Biblical Institute, 2006), §118.
5. Bruce K. Waltke and Michael O'Connor, *An Introduction to Biblical Hebrew Syntax* (Winona Lake: Eisenbrauns, 1990).
6. Joüon and Muraoka, *A Grammar of Biblical Hebrew*, §§119–121.
7. John A. Cook, "The Hebrew Verb: A Grammaticalization Approach," *Journal of Semitic Studies* 52 (2007): 239–280.
8. Robert D. Holmstedt, "The Relative Clause in Biblical Hebrew," in *Linguistic Studies in Ancient West Semitic* (2008).

9. Alviero Niccacci, *Syntax of the Verb in Classical Hebrew Prose* (Sheffield: JSOT Press, 1990).
10. Robert E. Longacre, *Joseph: A Story of Divine Providence* (Winona Lake: Eisenbrauns, 1989).

3. Wayyiqtol in the Narrative Structure of Biblical Hebrew

If the question of the *wayyiqtol* construction is moved from the sphere of purely morphological description to the sphere of its actual functioning in the text, it becomes clear that it represents one of the key mechanisms for organizing biblical narrative. Within the text of the Old Testament, *wayyiqtol* does not appear as a sporadic or stylistically neutral form, but rather as one of the primary markers of narrative progression. Contemporary syntactic and discourse-oriented studies generally agree that in prose narratives *wayyiqtol* typically marks the main storyline—that is, the sequence of events that propel the narrative forward—while other constructions are more frequently used to describe states, circumstances, background information, or commentary.¹

This function becomes particularly evident in the opening verses of the Book of Genesis. In Gen 1:1 we read:

בְּרֵאשִׁית בָּרָא אֱלֹהִים
bərē šīt bārā` ʿēlōhīm
 “In the beginning God created,”

and then in Gen 1:2:

וְהָאֲרֶץ הָיְתָה תוֹהוּ וָבֹהוּ
wə-hā`āreṣ hāyetāh tōhū wā-vōhū
 “And the earth was formless and void.”

Already at this point, an important textual distinction becomes apparent: verse 1:2 does not continue the narrative through a *wayyiqtol* form, but rather provides a description of a state. Only in Gen 1:3 does the characteristic narrative sequence begin:

וַיֹּאמֶר אֱלֹהִים יְהִי אוֹר
wayyō`mer ʿēlōhīm yəhî `ôr
 “And God said, ‘Let there be light.’”

This transition from a descriptive or circumstantial statement to a *wayyiqtol* form is one of the classical indicators that the main narrative line of creation begins in verse 1:3.²

In this sense, Genesis 1 represents an exceptionally instructive example of the distribution of verbal forms according to their discourse function. Verses 1:1–2 serve as introductory or antecedent information, while from verse 1:3 onward a sequence of *wayyiqtol* forms appears:

וַיֹּאמֶר (*wayyō`mer*)
 וַיְהִי (*wayəhî*)
 וַיַּרְא (*wayyar`*)

וַיַּבְדֵּל (wayyavdēl)
וַיִּקְרָא (wayyiqrā')

This sequence does not function as a mere accumulation of verbs, but rather as a carefully structured chain of successive creative acts. Daniel Bediako has shown, precisely on the basis of Genesis 1, that *wayyiqtol* clauses in this chapter carry the “narrative thread” of the text, while Gen 1:1–2 function as antecedent information that does not yet belong to the main sequence of the six-day creation narrative.³ Similarly, Jeremy Lyon observes that Gen 1:2 describes the state of the earth, while Gen 1:3 advances the narrative precisely through the *wayyiqtol* form.⁴

The same function becomes even clearer when one considers the internal organization of the individual days of creation. Each new creative act begins with the formula:

וַיֹּאמֶר אֱלֹהִים
wayyō'mer 'ēlōhīm
“And God said,”

followed by additional *wayyiqtol* forms describing fulfillment, evaluation, and naming. For example, in Gen 1:4:

וַיַּרְא אֱלֹהִים אֶת-הָאוֹר
wayyar 'ēlōhīm 'et-hā'ôr
“And God saw the light,”

followed by:

וַיַּבְדֵּל
wayyavdēl
“And he separated,”

and in Gen 1:5:

וַיִּקְרָא אֱלֹהִים
wayyiqrā' 'ēlōhīm
“And God called.”

Such usage demonstrates that *wayyiqtol* is not merely a past tense form, but a marker of sequentially organized actions within the narrative. It signals to the reader that the described events unfold as successive stages of the narrative progression.⁵

By contrast, constructions that stand outside the *wayyiqtol* chain typically perform a different function. In Gen 1:2, the form:

וַהֲאָרֶץ הָיְתָה
wə-hā'āreṣ hāyetāh

does not belong to the main sequence of events but describes a state. Similarly, nominal or participial constructions such as:

וְרוּחַ אֱלֹהִים מְרַחֶפֶת עַל-פְּנֵי הַמַּיִם
wə-rūaḥ ʾēlōhīm mərəḥefet ʿal-pəné hammāyim
“And the Spirit of God was hovering over the face of the waters,”

serve a background, descriptive function. The participle מְרַחֶפֶת (*mərəḥefet*) does not advance the narrative in the same way as *wayyiqtol*, but rather provides a descriptive frame. Thus, even within this micro-unit, a fundamental discourse distinction is visible: *wayyiqtol* carries the sequence of events, while other forms construct the scene or background.⁶

This distribution of verbal forms is not limited to the cosmogonic narrative of Genesis 1, but can also be observed in classical historical narratives. In the opening of the Book of Jonah, for example, Niccacci notes that the text begins with a *wayyiqtol* form and is followed by a sequence of similar forms that constitute the “main line” or “backbone” of the narrative.⁷

In Jonah 1:3 we read:

וַיִּקָּם יוֹנָה לְבָרֶחַ תַּרְשִׁישׁ
wayyāqām yōnāh livrōaḥ taršîšāh
“And Jonah arose to flee to Tarshish,”

followed by:

וַיֵּרֵד יָפוֹ
wayyēred yāpō
“And he went down to Joppa,”

וַיִּמְצָא אֲנִיָּה
wayyimšā ʾoniyyāh
“And he found a ship,”

וַיִּתֵּן שְׂכָרָהּ
wayyittēn śəkārāh
“And he paid its fare,”

וַיֵּרֵד בָּהּ
wayyēred bāh
“And he went down into it.”

This chain represents a rapid, linear narrative flow: the action is neither interrupted nor elaborated descriptively, but proceeds forward through a sequence of interconnected events.

At the same time, within the same narrative, other constructions appear that perform different discourse functions. When the text describes circumstances, states, or secondary information, it

employs forms such as *waw-x-qatal*, nominal clauses, or participles, rather than the *wayyiqtol* chain. Niccacci demonstrates, particularly in Jonah, that the main narrative line and background information can be distinguished by the choice of verbal form.⁸

This means that the selection of verbal forms in Biblical Hebrew is not merely a matter of tense, but also of textual hierarchy: certain forms carry the main action, while others indicate a secondary or explanatory level of discourse.

A similar pattern can be observed in the Joseph narrative in Genesis 37:

וַיֹּאמֶר לוֹ יִשְׂרָאֵל
wayyō`mer lô yiśrā`el
“And Israel said to him,”

וַיֵּלֶךְ יוֹסֵף
wayyēlek yōsēp
“And Joseph went,”

וַיִּמְצָאֵהוּ אִישׁ
wayyimšā`ēhū`iš
“And a man found him.”

Longacre demonstrated, precisely on the basis of the Joseph narrative, that chains of *wayyiqtol* forms typically carry the “storyline,” while other forms serve to slow down the narrative, provide explanation, or introduce additional information.⁹

The same principle is evident in historical narratives such as 1 Samuel 17, where central events are consistently expressed through *wayyiqtol* forms:

וַיִּקָּם דָּוִד
wayyāqām dāwid
“And David arose,”

וַיֵּטֵשׁ
wayyittōš
“And he left,”

וַיָּבֹא
wayyābō`
“And he came,”

וַיָּרָץ
wayyārāš
“And he ran.”

When the narrative advances, *wayyiqtol* dominates; when it describes a state, identifies participants, or introduces contextual information, other constructions are used. This corresponds to what modern discourse analysis identifies as the distinction between foreground and background information.¹⁰

The concept of foreground/background is thus central for understanding the function of *wayyiqtol*. In contemporary descriptions, *wayyiqtol* is regularly associated with foregrounded events—that is, those events that constitute the backbone of the narrative. Andrason’s overview of the literature shows that, despite differences in terminology, scholars widely recognize the same fundamental fact: *wayyiqtol* functions as the primary narrative form, while *x-qatal* and *x-yiqtol* more often serve background or perspective-shifting functions.¹¹

However, *wayyiqtol* should not be understood merely as a mechanical indicator of chronological succession. In some contexts, it introduces not simply the next event, but a decisive development in the narrative. For this reason, it is more accurate to interpret it as a marker of narrative progression rather than as a simple equivalent of the past tense in European languages.¹²

Footnotes

1. Bill T. Arnold and John H. Choi, *A Guide to Biblical Hebrew Syntax* (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2003); Alviero Niccacci, *Syntax of the Verb in Classical Hebrew Prose* (Sheffield: JSOT Press, 1990); Alexandre Andrason, “Biblical Hebrew Wayyiqtol: A Dynamic Definition,” *Journal of Hebrew Scriptures* 11 (2011): 1–58.
2. Jeremy D. Lyon, “Genesis 1:1–3 and the Literary Boundary of the First Day of Creation,” *Journal of the Evangelical Theological Society* 62/2 (2019): 269–285.
3. Daniel K. Bediako, “The Syntactic-Pragmatic Function of Genesis 1:1–2 in the Creation Narrative,” *Valley View University Journal of Theology* 3 (2014): 67–85.
4. Lyon, “Genesis 1:1–3,” 270–274.
5. Bruce K. Waltke and Michael O’Connor, *An Introduction to Biblical Hebrew Syntax* (Winona Lake: Eisenbrauns, 1990); Arnold and Choi, *A Guide to Biblical Hebrew Syntax*.
6. Bediako; Lyon.
7. Alviero Niccacci, “A Syntactic Analysis of Jonah,” esp. Jonah 1:1–5.
8. Ibid.
9. Robert E. Longacre, *Joseph: A Story of Divine Providence* (Winona Lake: Eisenbrauns, 1989).
10. Longacre; Niccacci.
11. Andrason, “Biblical Hebrew Wayyiqtol.”
12. Niccacci; Longacre; Bediako; Lyon.

4. Analysis of the Translational Tradition

One of the key elements for understanding the function of the *wayyiqtol* construction in Biblical Hebrew is the manner in which it has been transmitted through the history of translation. Translational tradition is not merely a neutral transfer of content from one language into another; it simultaneously shapes the way in which readers perceive the structure of the source text. In the

case of Biblical Hebrew, particularly in narrative sections, the translation of the prefix ו (waw) has had far-reaching consequences for the interpretation of the verbal system itself.¹

As demonstrated in the preceding chapters, within Hebrew narrative the *wayyiqtol* construction typically marks the sequential flow of events that constitute the main line of narration.² However, within the translational tradition this construction has almost consistently been interpreted as a coordinative structure, that is, as a combination of the conjunction “and” with a verb. This interpretation finds its origin in the earliest major translation of the Hebrew Bible—the Greek Septuagint.³

4.1 The Septuagint and Greek Narrative Structure

In the Septuagint, *wayyiqtol* is most commonly rendered by means of the Greek conjunction καί (“and”) combined with the aorist tense of the verb. This pattern is highly consistent and can already be observed in the opening verses of Genesis.⁴

The Hebrew text of Gen 1:3 reads:

וַיֹּאמֶר אֱלֹהִים יְהִי אוֹר
wayyō ’mer ’ēlōhīm yāhî ’ôr
“And God said: ‘Let there be light.’”

The Septuagint translates:

καὶ εἶπεν ὁ θεός· γενεθήτω φῶς
kai eipen ho theos: genēthētō phōs
“And God said: ‘Let there be light.’”⁵

A similar pattern appears in the following verse:

Hebrew:

וַיַּרְא אֱלֹהִים אֶת-הָאוֹר
wayyar ’ ’ēlōhīm ’et-hā ’ôr

Septuagint:

καὶ εἶδεν ὁ θεός τὸ φῶς
kai eiden ho theos to phōs
“And God saw the light.”⁶

In Classical Greek, the conjunction καί can perform a narrative function and often introduces the next event in a story. However, when later translations transferred this structure into European languages, it increasingly came to be interpreted as a literal coordinating conjunction.⁷

4.2 The Latin Vulgate

In the Latin Vulgate, translated by Jerome at the end of the fourth century, the Greek structure is largely preserved. The *wayyiqtol* construction is almost regularly rendered through *et + verb*.⁸

Gen 1:3

et dixit Deus fiat lux

“And God said: ‘Let there be light.’”⁹

Gen 1:4

et vidit Deus lucem

“And God saw the light.”¹⁰

The Latin conjunction *et* functions as a coordinating conjunction, but within Latin narrative style it often served as a narrative marker as well. Nevertheless, when European translations were produced under the strong influence of the Vulgate, this structure increasingly came to be understood as a literal “and.”¹¹

4.3 The European Translational Tradition

The influence of the Septuagint and the Vulgate can be traced throughout virtually all later translations of the Bible. The following examples illustrate this phenomenon across a wide range of languages:

Hebrew:

וַיֹּאמֶר אֱלֹהִים
wayyō ’mer ’ēlōhīm

Examples of translations:

English –

“And God said...” (King James Version)¹²

German –

“Und Gott sprach...” (Luther Bible)¹³

French –

« Et Dieu dit... » (Louis Segond)¹⁴

Spanish –

“Y dijo Dios...” (Reina-Valera)¹⁵

Portuguese –

“E disse Deus...” (Almeida Revista e Corrigida)¹⁶

Italian –

“E Dio disse...” (CEI Bible)¹⁷

Dutch –

“En God zei...” (Statenvertaling)¹⁸

Swedish –

“Och Gud sade...” (Svenska Folkbibeln)¹⁹

Danish –

“Og Gud sagde...” (Bibelen 1871)²⁰

Norwegian –

“Og Gud sa...” (Bibelen 1930)²¹

Polish –

“I rzekł Bóg...” (Biblia Tysiąclecia)²²

Czech –

“I řekl Bůh...” (Bible kralická)²³

Slovak –

“A Boh povedal...” (Roháček translation)²⁴

Hungarian –

“És mondta Isten...” (Károli Bible)²⁵

Finnish –

“Ja Jumala sanoi...” (Kirkkoraamattu 1933/38)²⁶

Russian –

“И сказал Бог...” (Synodal Translation)²⁷

Ukrainian –

“І сказав Бог...” (Ohiienko translation)²⁸

Bulgarian –

“И рече Бог...” (Bulgarian Bible 1940)²⁹

Greek (Modern) –
« Και εἶπε ὁ Θεός... »³⁰

Romanian –
“Și Dumnezeu a zis...” (Cornilescu Bible)³¹

Croatian –
“I reče Bog...” (Zagreb Bible)³²

Serbian –
“I reče Bog...” (Daničić–Karadžić translation)³³

In all these languages, the same translational pattern is clearly visible: the *wayyiqtol* construction is consistently rendered as “conjunction + verb.”

4.4 Consequences of This Translational Model

This mode of translation has several important consequences for the interpretation of the biblical text.

First, it creates the impression that Hebrew narrative operates as a sequence of coordinated clauses. However, modern linguistic research demonstrates that the function of *wayyiqtol* is primarily discourse-based rather than coordinative.³⁴

Second, the frequent use of the conjunction “and” produces a distinctive style that has become characteristic of biblical translations. This style often appears archaic and differs from the narrative conventions of modern languages.

Third, such translation may obscure the distinction between the main narrative line (*foreground*) and background information (*background*). As Niccacci and Longacre have demonstrated, *wayyiqtol* typically marks events that advance the action, while other constructions describe states or circumstances.³⁵

This distinction can be illustrated by the following example from Genesis 37:

וַיֵּלֶךְ יוֹסֵף אַחֲרֵי אֶחָיו
wayyēlek yōsēp ’aḥar ’ehāyw

Traditional translation:
“And Joseph went after his brothers.”

Discourse-oriented rendering:
“Then Joseph went after his brothers.”

In other words, *wayyiqtol* marks the next step in the narrative, rather than merely coordinating clauses.

The analysis of the translational tradition demonstrates that the model “and + verb” is deeply embedded in European biblical culture. This model originates in the Septuagint, is transmitted through the Vulgate, and continues in most modern translations. While such a translation is not necessarily incorrect, it may influence how readers understand the function of the *wayyiqtol* construction.

Contemporary linguistic research increasingly emphasizes that in the Hebrew text *wayyiqtol* functions primarily as a marker of narrative sequence rather than as a simple coordinating conjunction. Recognizing this distinction is crucial both for interpreting the biblical text and for developing more precise translation strategies.

Footnotes

1. Bruce K. Waltke and Michael O'Connor, *An Introduction to Biblical Hebrew Syntax* (Winona Lake: Eisenbrauns, 1990), 543–552.
2. Alviero Niccacci, *Syntax of the Verb in Classical Hebrew Prose* (Sheffield: JSOT Press, 1990), 31–56.
3. Emanuel Tov, *Textual Criticism of the Hebrew Bible*, 3rd ed. (Minneapolis: Fortress Press, 2012), 131–140.
4. Paul Joüon and Takamitsu Muraoka, *A Grammar of Biblical Hebrew* (Rome: Pontifical Biblical Institute, 2006), §§118–119.
5. *Septuaginta: Vetus Testamentum Graecum*, ed. Alfred Rahlfs and Robert Hanhart (Stuttgart: Deutsche Bibelgesellschaft, 2006), Gen 1:3.
6. *Ibid.*, Gen 1:4.
7. Stanley E. Porter, *Idioms of the Greek New Testament* (Sheffield: Sheffield Academic Press, 1992), 188–192.
8. Jerome, *Biblia Sacra Vulgata*, ed. Robert Weber and Roger Gryson (Stuttgart: Deutsche Bibelgesellschaft, 2007).
9. *Ibid.*, Gen 1:3.
10. *Ibid.*, Gen 1:4.
11. Sebastian Brock, “Aspects of Translation Technique in Antiquity,” *Greek, Roman and Byzantine Studies* 20 (1979): 69–87.
12. *The Holy Bible: King James Version* (London, 1611), Gen 1:3.
13. *Die Bibel nach der Übersetzung Martin Luthers* (Stuttgart: Deutsche Bibelgesellschaft, 1984).
14. *La Sainte Bible: Version Louis Segond* (Paris: Alliance Biblique Universelle, 1910).
15. *Biblia Reina-Valera* (Madrid: Sociedades Bíblicas Unidas, 1960).
16. *Bíblia Almeida Revista e Corrigida* (Rio de Janeiro: Sociedade Bíblica do Brasil, 1995).
17. *La Sacra Bibbia CEI* (Roma: Conferenza Episcopale Italiana, 2008).
18. *Statenvertaling* (Leiden, 1637).
19. *Svenska Folkbibeln* (Stockholm: Stiftelsen Svenska Folkbibeln, 1998).
20. *Bibelen* (Copenhagen: Det Danske Bibelselskab, 1871).
21. *Bibelen* (Oslo: Det Norske Bibelselskap, 1930).

22. *Biblia Tysiąclecia* (Poznań: Pallottinum, 2003).
23. *Bible kralická* (Prague: Česká biblická společnost).
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25. *Károli Biblia* (Budapest: Magyar Bibliatársulat).
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27. Синодальный перевод Библии (Moscow: Russian Bible Society).
28. Библия переклад Івана Огієнка (Kyiv: Ukrainian Bible Society).
29. Българска Библия (Sofia: Bulgarian Bible Society, 1940).
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32. *Zagrebačka Biblija* (Zagreb: Kršćanska sadašnjost, 1968).
33. Vuk Karadžić and Đuro Daničić, *Sveto pismo Staroga i Novoga zavjeta* (Vienna, 1868).
34. John A. Cook, “The Hebrew Verb: A Grammaticalization Approach,” *Journal of Semitic Studies* 52 (2007): 239–280.
35. Robert E. Longacre, *Joseph: A Story of Divine Providence* (Winona Lake: Eisenbrauns, 1989); Niccacci, *Syntax of the Verb*, 45–52.

5. Reconsidering the Function of *Waw*: Toward a Discourse-Based Interpretation

The analysis presented in the previous chapters has shown that the traditional interpretation of the *wayyiqtol* construction as a combination of a coordinating conjunction and a verb is largely rooted in the history of translation rather than in the internal structure of Biblical Hebrew itself. This observation opens the possibility for a reassessment of the function of the prefix ו (*waw*) within this construction.

In classical grammatical descriptions, *waw* has almost universally been identified as a coordinating conjunction equivalent to “and.”¹ This assumption has strongly influenced both the analysis of the Hebrew verbal system and the translation of biblical texts. However, when *wayyiqtol* is examined within the framework of discourse analysis, it becomes evident that the role of *waw* cannot be fully explained in purely coordinative terms.

5.1 The Limits of the Coordinative Interpretation

If *waw* in the *wayyiqtol* construction functioned primarily as a coordinating conjunction, one would expect it to behave in a manner analogous to conjunctions in Indo-European languages. In such languages, coordination typically links elements of equal syntactic and semantic status. However, the behavior of *wayyiqtol* in Biblical Hebrew suggests a different pattern.²

In narrative texts, sequences of *wayyiqtol* forms do not merely coordinate clauses but create a hierarchical structure in which each subsequent form advances the storyline.³ This is particularly evident in passages such as Genesis 22:

וַיִּקַּח אַבְרָהָם אֶת־עֵצֵי הַעֹלָה
wayyiqqah 'abrāhām 'et- 'āšē hā 'ōlāh
“And Abraham took the wood of the burnt offering,”

וַיִּשֶׂם עַל־יִצְחָק בְּנוֹ
wayyāšem 'al-yiṣḥāq bənō
“And he placed it on Isaac his son,”

וַיִּקַּח בְּיָדוֹ אֶת־הָאֵשׁ
wayyiqqah bəyādō 'et-hā 'ēš
“And he took in his hand the fire,”

וַיֵּלְכוּ שְׁנֵיהֶם יַחְדָּו
wayyēlkū šənēhem yaḥdāw
“And the two of them went together.”

In this sequence, the repeated presence of *waw* does not introduce independent clauses of equal status but rather organizes a tightly connected chain of actions. The narrative progression is linear and cumulative, with each *wayyiqtol* form representing a step in the unfolding event.⁴

From a discourse perspective, such sequences function less as coordination and more as narrative chaining. The prefix *waw* thus appears to be part of a larger grammaticalized structure that signals the continuation of the narrative line.⁵

5.2 Waw as a Marker of Narrative Continuity

Modern linguistic approaches increasingly interpret *wayyiqtol* as a specialized verbal form whose primary function is to indicate sequential progression within a narrative.⁶ Within this framework, the prefix *waw* is not treated as an independent conjunction but as an integral component of a grammaticalized construction.

Evidence for this interpretation can be observed in the distribution of verbal forms within narrative texts. As shown in previous chapters, *wayyiqtol* regularly appears in contexts where the narrative advances, while other constructions—such as *qatal*, *yiqtol*, participles, or nominal clauses—are used to describe states, background information, or explanatory material.⁷

This contrast can be illustrated by the following example:

וַיָּבֹא יוֹסֵף אֶל־אָחָיו
wayyābō 'yôsēp 'el- 'ehāyw
“And Joseph came to his brothers,”

versus:

וַיִּסַּף הַיּוֹסֵף אֶת־הַצֹּאן
wə-yôsēp hāyāh rō'eh 'et-haššō'n
“Now Joseph was tending the flock.”

In the first case, *wayyiqtol* advances the narrative, while in the second, the construction describes a state or ongoing situation. The presence of *waw* in both examples demonstrates that its function cannot be reduced to simple coordination.⁸

Instead, it appears that Biblical Hebrew distinguishes between different types of *waw*-constructions, each associated with a specific discourse function.⁹ The *wayyiqtol* construction, in particular, signals the continuation of the main narrative line and thus plays a central role in structuring the text.

5.3 The Role of Grammaticalization

The interpretation of *wayyiqtol* as a unified construction is supported by theories of grammaticalization. From this perspective, linguistic elements that originally had independent meanings may, over time, become integrated into fixed grammatical structures.¹⁰

Several scholars have suggested that the *wayyiqtol* construction developed historically from earlier forms in which *waw* functioned as a conjunction.¹¹ However, through repeated use in narrative contexts, the combination of *waw* and the verbal form became conventionalized as a marker of sequential past events.

John Cook, for example, argues that *wayyiqtol* should be understood as part of a grammaticalized system of aspect and discourse functions rather than as a mechanical combination of conjunction and verb.¹² In this view, the prefix *waw* has lost its independent semantic value and has become a structural marker within a specific verbal form.

This perspective explains why *wayyiqtol* behaves differently from simple coordination. While conjunctions in Indo-European languages can often be omitted without fundamentally altering the structure of a sentence, the removal of *waw* from *wayyiqtol* would disrupt the narrative flow and change the grammatical form itself.¹³

5.4 Implications for Translation

If *wayyiqtol* is understood primarily as a marker of narrative progression rather than as a conjunction, this has important consequences for translation. The traditional rendering “and + verb” may, in many cases, obscure the discourse function of the construction.¹⁴

For example:

וַיָּאָמֶן מֹשֶׁה
wayyāqām mōšeh

Traditional translation:
“And Moses arose.”

Discourse-oriented translation:
“Then Moses arose.”

The latter rendering more clearly reflects the sequential nature of the action. In some contexts, it may even be appropriate to omit the conjunction altogether and translate simply as:

“Moses arose.”

Such an approach aligns more closely with the narrative conventions of modern languages, which often avoid excessive coordination and instead rely on syntactic and contextual cues to indicate sequence.¹⁵

However, it is important to emphasize that no single translation strategy can be applied uniformly to all instances of *wayyiqtol*. The appropriate rendering depends on the broader context, including the rhythm of the narrative, stylistic considerations, and the expectations of the target audience.

5.5 Toward an Integrated Model

The analysis presented in this study suggests that the traditional understanding of *waw* as a coordinating conjunction is insufficient to account for its role within the *wayyiqtol* construction. Instead, a more adequate explanation must take into account the discourse function of this form within the structure of biblical narrative.

Within such a model, *wayyiqtol* is understood as a specialized narrative form that signals the progression of events along the main storyline. The prefix *waw* is not an independent conjunction but part of a grammaticalized structure that has developed historically and acquired a specific discourse function.¹⁶

This approach allows for a more coherent explanation of the distribution of verbal forms in Biblical Hebrew and resolves many of the difficulties associated with the traditional theory of *waw conversive*. At the same time, it provides a framework for re-evaluating the translational tradition and developing more precise strategies for rendering biblical narrative in modern languages. See also Željko Stanojević, *Hebrejsko-srpski rečnik* (Beograd: Rad; Alfa i Omega, 2001).

Footnotes

1. Wilhelm Gesenius, *Gesenius' Hebrew Grammar*, ed. E. Kautzsch, rev. A. E. Cowley (Oxford: Clarendon Press, 1910), §§111–112.
2. Bruce K. Waltke and Michael O'Connor, *An Introduction to Biblical Hebrew Syntax* (Winona Lake: Eisenbrauns, 1990), 543–552.
3. Alviero Niccacci, *Syntax of the Verb in Classical Hebrew Prose* (Sheffield: JSOT Press, 1990), 31–56.
4. Robert E. Longacre, *Joseph: A Story of Divine Providence* (Winona Lake: Eisenbrauns, 1989).
5. Alexandre Andrason, “Biblical Hebrew Wayyiqtol: A Dynamic Definition,” *Journal of Hebrew Scriptures* 11 (2011): 1–58.
6. Bill T. Arnold and John H. Choi, *A Guide to Biblical Hebrew Syntax* (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2003).
7. Niccacci, *Syntax of the Verb*; Waltke and O'Connor.
8. Arnold and Choi; Joüon and Muraoka.
9. Joüon and Muraoka, *A Grammar of Biblical Hebrew*, §§118–121.
10. Paul J. Hopper and Elizabeth Closs Traugott, *Grammaticalization* (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2003).
11. Waltke and O'Connor; Cook.
12. John A. Cook, “The Hebrew Verb: A Grammaticalization Approach,” *Journal of Semitic Studies* 52 (2007): 239–280.
13. Hopper and Traugott.
14. Niccacci; Longacre.
15. Eugene A. Nida, *Toward a Science of Translating* (Leiden: Brill, 1964).
16. Andrason; Cook; Niccacci.

6. Conclusion

The analysis presented in this study has sought to reassess the function of the *wayyiqtol* construction in Biblical Hebrew by integrating insights from grammatical description, discourse analysis, and the history of translation. The results of this investigation demonstrate that the traditional interpretation of *wayyiqtol* as a combination of a coordinating conjunction and a verb—commonly expressed through the concept of *waw conversive*—is insufficient to account for the full range of its linguistic and textual functions.¹

The examination of narrative texts has shown that *wayyiqtol* functions as a primary marker of sequential progression within Biblical Hebrew prose. It serves to structure the narrative by signaling the main line of events, distinguishing it from background information expressed through other verbal forms such as *qatal*, *yiqtol*, participles, and nominal clauses.² This distribution of forms reflects a hierarchical organization of discourse rather than a simple system of tense distinctions.

At the same time, the historical analysis of the translational tradition has revealed that the widespread rendering of *wayyiqtol* as “and + verb” is largely the result of the influence of the Septuagint and the Latin Vulgate.³ Through these translations, the prefix ו (*waw*) came to be consistently interpreted as a coordinating conjunction, a view that has been perpetuated in most European languages. However, this translational convention does not necessarily reflect the underlying structure of the Hebrew text.

From the perspective of modern linguistics, particularly discourse analysis and theories of grammaticalization, *wayyiqtol* is more accurately understood as a unified verbal form with a specific narrative function.⁴ Within this framework, the prefix *waw* is not an independent conjunction but an integral component of a grammaticalized construction that signals the continuation of the narrative sequence. This interpretation aligns with the findings of contemporary scholars who emphasize the role of *wayyiqtol* in marking foregrounded events and advancing the storyline.⁵

The implications of this analysis are significant both for the study of Biblical Hebrew and for the practice of translation. Recognizing the discourse function of *wayyiqtol* allows for a more precise understanding of the structure of biblical narrative and provides a basis for evaluating traditional translation strategies. While the rendering “and + verb” may preserve certain stylistic features of the text, it can also obscure the distinction between sequential progression and simple coordination.⁶

Accordingly, this study suggests that greater attention should be paid to the narrative function of *wayyiqtol* in translation. In some contexts, alternative renderings—such as “then,” or even the omission of an explicit conjunction—may more accurately reflect the dynamics of the Hebrew text. However, such decisions must always be made with sensitivity to the broader literary and stylistic context.

Finally, this study contributes to the broader discussion of the Hebrew verbal system by demonstrating the importance of integrating grammatical, discourse, and translational perspectives. The *wayyiqtol* construction cannot be adequately explained within a purely morphological framework, nor can it be fully understood without considering the historical processes that have shaped its interpretation.

In conclusion, *wayyiqtol* should be regarded not as a mechanical combination of conjunction and verb, but as a central element of the narrative system of Biblical Hebrew—a form whose primary function is to structure the progression of events within the text. This perspective not only resolves long-standing difficulties associated with the theory of *waw conversive*, but also opens new avenues for the analysis and translation of biblical narrative.

Footnotes

1. Wilhelm Gesenius, *Gesenius' Hebrew Grammar*, ed. E. Kautzsch, rev. A. E. Cowley (Oxford: Clarendon Press, 1910), §§111–112.

2. Alviero Niccacci, *Syntax of the Verb in Classical Hebrew Prose* (Sheffield: JSOT Press, 1990); Bruce K. Waltke and Michael O'Connor, *An Introduction to Biblical Hebrew Syntax* (Winona Lake: Eisenbrauns, 1990).
3. Emanuel Tov, *Textual Criticism of the Hebrew Bible*, 3rd ed. (Minneapolis: Fortress Press, 2012); Jerome, *Biblia Sacra Vulgata*.
4. John A. Cook, "The Hebrew Verb: A Grammaticalization Approach," *Journal of Semitic Studies* 52 (2007): 239–280; Paul J. Hopper and Elizabeth Closs Traugott, *Grammaticalization* (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2003).
5. Alexandre Andrason, "Biblical Hebrew Wayyiqtol: A Dynamic Definition," *Journal of Hebrew Scriptures* 11 (2011): 1–58; Robert E. Longacre, *Joseph: A Story of Divine Providence* (Winona Lake: Eisenbrauns, 1989).
6. Eugene A. Nida, *Toward a Science of Translating* (Leiden: Brill, 1964).

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